

Synthesis of novel ZnFe₂O₄/CaWO₄/clinoptilolite zeolite nanocomposite and its performance for the destruction of sulfur mustard agent simulant 2-chloroethyl phenyl sulfide (2-CEPS)

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Abstract

In this study, CaWO₄ and ZnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully immobilized in the framework of clinoptilolite zeolite through the ultrasonic-assisted hydrothermal approach to achieve the novel ZnFe₂O₄/CaWO₄/clinoptilolite nanocomposite catalyst and analyzed via FE-SEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD, and VSM. Subsequently, the ZnFe₂O₄/CaWO₄/clinoptilolite nanocomposite performance for the destruction of toxic sulfur mustard agent simulant 2-chloroethyl phenyl sulfide (2-CEPS) was checked by using GC-FID and GC-MS analyses. The gained GC-FID outcomes indicated that 2-CEPS agent simulant was completely destructed in the presence of the ZnFe₂O₄/CaWO₄/clinoptilolite nanocomposite in n-decane solvent after 30 min of contact time. Ultimately, 2-hydroxyl ethyl phenyl sulfide (2-HEPS) and phenyl vinyl sulfide (PVS) as the hydrolysis and elimination products of 2-CEPS were distinguished, respectively. This revealed that the ZnFe₂O₄/CaWO₄/clinoptilolite nanocomposite could potentially be applied as an effective decontaminant of hazardous chemical agents.

Keywords: ZnFe₂O₄/CaWO₄/clinoptilolite, zeolite, nanocomposite, 2-CEPS, destruction, hydrolysis, elimination.